

FILMUNIVERSITÄT
BABELSBERG
KONRAD WOLF

**Filmuni
proudly presents
#03**

Die fotografischen Arbeiten, die für Covergestaltung und zur Strukturierung der vorliegenden Publikation verwendet werden, stammen aus der Serie LAYERS von Jonas Ludwig Walter. Ausgangspunkt ist der Blick in den Zwischenraum zwischen Kinosaal und Projektionskabine, wo sich die immateriellen Bilder auf dem Weg zur Leinwand mit der Materialität des Raumes vermengen zu neuen, flüchtigen Bildgefügen. Die Arbeiten sind als Dialog mit den verschiedenen Forschungsfeldern der Filmuniversität konzipiert.

Jonas Ludwig Walter hat ein Studium an der renommierten Ostkreuzschule für Fotografie in Berlin absolviert sowie einen Master-Abschluss im Studiengang Regie an der Filmuniversität.

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**Forschungs- und Transferbericht
der Filmuniversität Babelsberg
KONRAD WOLF
2022/23**

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From Gezi to Berlin

A Personal Journey Through Video Activism

Amidst the sociopolitical challenges in Turkey, video activism has emerged as a key tool of resistance against the growing restrictions on freedom of expression. Its strength lies in its capacity to give a voice to the voiceless, defy the suppression of truth, and illuminate the injustices that would otherwise remain hidden. My journey into this realm started during the Gezi Park Protests in Istanbul in the summer of 2013. Picking up a camera and heading to the protests felt like the most natural response to the extraordinary times we were living in, times that demanded documentation. As I watched police brutality escalate during the park's occupation, it became evident that traditional media channels were failing to represent the full scope of the events. Instead, they framed the protests as morally incompatible with Turkish values, instigated by foreign forces aiming to disrupt the Turkish economy. This urgent need to document gave birth to *I Occupied: The Gezi Park Protests*, an audio-visual diary that not only chronicled my personal journey but also marked the beginning of my collaboration with video activists in Turkey. It was during these tumultuous times that my academic and practical exploration of video activism's profound potential for social change began to take shape.

This initial endeavor was more than a creative outlet; it was a response to the growing urgency of the situation, where information was weaponized, and truth systematically obscured. As I immersed myself in this medium, I forged connections with video activist groups across Turkey. Their unwavering commitment to amplifying marginalized voices in the face of censorship and propaganda left an indelible mark on me. I realized that the role of video activism extended beyond documenting events; it became an essential channel for expressing dissent, fostering resilience, and uniting communities, all while preserving the audio-visual memory of that historical period.

My academic and practical interest in video activism as a means of empowerment for marginalized communities and a weapon against media censorship faced obstacles. Academic freedoms were increasingly restricted, reaching a climax with extensive purges in 2016–2017. These purges extended into various spheres during the state of emergency declared in the post-coup d'état period, suppressing dissenting voices across academia, media, the judiciary, and beyond, eradicating critical perspectives and leading to a significant wave of migration.

In this climate of academic uncertainty and the ever-pressing importance of video activism in Turkey, the concept for *VIDEOACT: The Use of Video as a Tool of Self-Representation for Turkish Practitioners in Germany* began to take shape. It was a project born from the fusion of my academic aspirations and my commitment to shedding light on the activities of video activists, the risks they have been taking, and the consequences they have had to face, including intimidation, threats, targeting, detention, and even imprisonment. This project emerged as a result of my keen observation that video activists were leaving Turkey, becoming part of a new wave of migration triggered in the post-Gezi era and intensified during the post-coup period. Thus, the project held interdisciplinary significance, straddling in the fields of media studies, activism, migration studies and ethnography.

The project's core premise revolved around the idea of self-representation as a powerful tool for individuals facing suppression and marginalization. It sought to explore how Turkish practitioners in Germany, a community shaped by waves of migration, harnessed video as a means of articulating their experiences, voicing their perspectives, and asserting their presence in a foreign land. This endeavor was driven by a profound curiosity: How did the medium of video transcend geographical and cultural boundaries to empower individuals in the diaspora to convey their unique narratives?

Online platforms served as the nexus for various forms of protest documentation, political mash-up videos, and news videos, all rallying around the issues affecting Berlin and its residents. In this vibrant ecosystem, digital media archival practices resonated powerfully, driven by the urgent need to preserve cultural memory. Fundamentally, video activists found themselves in a unique position to sustain their work. Berlin's political climate not only encouraged active involvement in local issues but also facilitated remote engagement with the unfolding events in the activists' countries of origin. Moreover, the landscape in Berlin transcended national borders to form transnational alliances, their interconnectedness underscoring the shared struggles and aspirations for better futures.

As the project unfolded, I found myself immersed in embedded ethnography, a process that involved participant observation, ongoing interactive exchanges, and interviews. Through these interactions, I cultivated networks that not only enriched my research but deepened my understanding of the intricate tapestry of migration, identity, and video activism. Additionally, the project presented a unique challenge of combatting my own bias. Given my personal background and emotional connection to the stories I was being told, there were instances where the line between my role as a researcher and that of a (video) activist became blurred.

These encounters led to the organization of impactful events, including screenings, workshops, and panel discussions. These initiatives served as platforms for delving deeper into our collective comprehension of these multifaceted concepts and fostering a broader dialogue within different communities. Collaborations with cultural institutions and events, including the HAU Hebel am Ufer, the Maxim Gorki Theatre, and the Sehnsüchte International Student Film Festival, played a pivotal role in communicating and disseminating the project's areas of investigation. These partnerships allowed me to reach wider audiences and extend the project's reach, contributing significantly to the overall impact of my work. These outreach activities stood as a testament to the transformative potential of transnational activism and the profound influence of film as a catalyst for change.

One of the most striking observations I had with regards to audio-visual production by practitioners from Turkey in Germany was the affective quality of the work. The emotional impact of the migratory journey echoes in the works, akin to the various stages of grief, with the emotional impact evolving over time. Many media grapple with the reality of migration, the profound implications of uprooting, displacement and reconfiguring political subjectivity. They explore the delicate balance between staying connected to one's homeland while grounding oneself in a new environment. Several documentaries and fiction shorts, such as *Other Than That, I'm Fine* (2018, Eren Aksu), *Ghostly* (S. Buse Yıldırım, 2020), *Tower* (Emre Birışmen, 2022), and *9/8fight41: a 9/8 fight for all of us* (Gizem Aksu, 2022), center their narratives on migration and its profound impacts on the body, relationships, and the reconfiguration of cultural reference points. Other films delved deep into themes of belonging and homing, while unearthing the socio-political realities of integration, racism, and patriarchal oppression: *Welcomed to Germany?* (Özlem Sarıyıldız, 2018), *Gurbet is a Home Now* (Pınar Öğrenci, 2021), *Bitter and Sweet* (Didem Şahin, 2021), and *Köy* (Serpil Turhan, 2021) explore the realities of migration through a historical lens, drawing connections between new waves of migration and those of the past, with a particular focus on the stories of women. These films seek to capture the memory of migration and envision futures where our realities are not just acknowledged but actively heard, paving the way for better tomorrows.

A common thread woven through these films is the notion that migration itself has become synonymous with activism. Living as a migrant necessitates a daily struggle against prejudice. Migrants must assert their realities and stories within the broader European context. They must actively counter the media's portrayal of them as perpetrators of violence, helpless victims, or backward barbarians according to predefined narratives about their place in European societies.

Addressing these realities is of utmost importance, for it represents one of the most pressing issues that Europe needs to grapple with, particularly within the context of global migration dynamics. One thing is certain: Berlin is transforming, and the stories of newcomers cannot be denied. They are becoming integral to the narratives shaping the city. Practitioners are not merely amplifying the voices from movements from home; they carry the very essence of these movements wherever they go. Their actions, their films, their alliances—all stand as a testament to their unwavering commitment to the pursuit of justice, truth, and the amplification of voices that refuse to be silenced. In the end, they are the protagonists in a collective endeavor to create a more inclusive and empathetic world, extending the broader significance of their work beyond Berlin's borders.

Dr. Şirin Fulya Erensoy, Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellow 2021–2023

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Impressum

Herausgeberin:

Filmuniversität Babelsberg
KONRAD WOLF

V.i.S.d.P

Prof. Dr. Susanne Stürmer, Präsidentin

Redaktion:

Dr. Stella Donata Haag,
Leitung Forschung | Transfer | Akademischer Nachwuchs

Julia Diebel, Pressesprecherin |
Leitung des Bereichs Kommunikation
& Marketing

Susanne Kern,
Kommunikation & Marketing

Satz & Gestaltung:

giraffentoast design gmbh,
Kleiner Schäferkamp 28, 20357 Hamburg

Druck:

K+L PrintMedia GmbH
Christian-Henkel-Straße 5, 12349 Berlin

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